

Assessment of Innovative Material Resources for Manpower Development of Brick/Block Laying and Concreting Trade Students in Technical Colleges in Rivers State.

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ABSTRACT

The study assessed the innovative materials resources for manpower development of brick/block laying and concreting trade students in Technical Colleges in Rivers State. Specifically, the study sought to assess innovative tools, innovative material resources, and innovative machines for manpower development of brick/block laying and concreting trade students in Technical Colleges in Rivers State. The study adopted a descriptive survey design. The population of the study comprised 15 building instructors totally 25, in the three technical colleges in Rivers State. The population was manageable and hence, was used for the study. Therefore, no sample method was adopted in the study. Three objectives were formulated answered and tested at .05 level of significance. The instrument used for the study was a survey questionnaire. The instrument was face validated by two Vocational Technology Education lecturers in Rivers State University, Port Harcourt and it was tested for reliability using Cronbach Alpha reliability co-efficient method. A reliability value of .82 was obtained. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research question while t-test statistical tool was used to test the hypothesis. The study found that; measuring wheel, polishers, vacuum blowers, virtual and augmented reality (CR/VR) Project in Hydraulic brick/block making machines, concrete floor grinding machines, high efficiency electric wall screed machine and among others are the innovative material resources for manpower development of brick/block laying and concreting trade students in technical colleges in rivers state. Therefore it was recommended that government should ensure that the expected innovative tool, instructional materials and machines are provided in brick/block laying and concreting trade programmes for adequate manpower development.

Keywords: Innovative, Material Resources, Manpower Development, Brick/Block Laying, Concreting Trade, Students.

INTRODUCTION

Manpower development is an essential ingredient needed in brick/block laying and concreting trade for the growth of the economy. The integral part of manpower development is basically concerned with increasing of adequate knowledge and requisite skills set aside for performing brick/block laying jobs. Globally, manpower development activities are carried out in technical school to improve the idea of students in brick/block laying for industrial purpose. Manpower development has received a broader consideration with the emergence of current globalization and unstable job issues in the present Nigeria economy (Obi-Anike, et al, 2017). It has taken a new dimension in the 21st century

compared to what was obtained in the past. Manpower development is a process that seeks to optimize an organization usage of its human resources. It require an integrated approach that addresses the multi-dimensional aspects for enhancing employees with brick /block laying skills as applied to the current trend in globalization since the world is now technologically driven.

Several scholars have proven that manpower development remains a good mechanism for enhancing brick/block laying and concreting skills needed in the present and future accomplishment in construction industry. Anyonike et al (2015) posited that brick/block laying and concreting (B/BC) is one of the trade at the National Technical Certificate (NTC) level and its curriculum primarily aimed at equipping an individual with skills on the application of right or appropriate blocks, tools and concrete as applicable in the construction industry.

However, due to technology advancement, brick/block laying and concreting innovative tools are necessary in the construction industry to achieve a good result. The National Board for Technical Education (NBTE, 2012) opined that brick/block laying and concreting trade is offered in technical colleges at both manpower developments. Equally, brick/block laying in technical college curriculum encompasses the innovative skills needed in accomplishing given tasks of blocks, rendering of walls, wall tiling, pointing top walls and laying of curved walls (Arches). Brick/block laying and concreting is designed to provide the trainee with essential knowledge and skill that will enable graduates perform competently in all aspect of brick/block work in construction industry (Awurum, 2005).

Brick/block lying and concreting trade acquisition is mostly characterized by modern innovations associated with tools machines and instructional materials for manpower development. Over the years brick/block laying and concreting programmes has been facing the challenges of lack of innovative resources in Nigeria. Nwafor and Ali (2015) maintained that innovation has to do with changes leading to improvement in dynamics and creating of new things out of the existing ones. Similarly, innovative materials resources are new sustainable designed materials with enhanced functionalities and application in wide ranges of brick/block laying instructional process.

These innovative instructional materials resource buttresses on the encouraging varieties of instructional method which are currently used in brick/block laying and concreting trades, progammes such as blogs, wikis, social networking sites, virtual leaning environment (VLE) laptops, net books, tablets PCS, interactive white board, simulation and many more. Nworie et al (2020) posited that examples of instructional resources include variety of sources and media formats including online resources such as text, print photos, graphics, animations, simulations, sounds, videos and among others. It is a clear fact that varieties of innovative construction machines in brick/block laying and concreting have been developed to make job easier in construction industry.

United Nation Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) (2019) averred that most developments in brick/block laying and concreting are the innovative machines that can make job easier in the construction process. Today a lot of machine models in brick/block laying and concreting have been designed with technological innovations to produce a wide range of concrete products like solid/hollow block, interlocks pavers, kerb stones and developing standard in plastering, rendering, screed and among other at quicker cycle in construction industry. Above all, this ear of technological advancement has it that in technical colleges brick/block laying a concreting trade programmes and assets are designed without innovative resources that will in turn enable students to fit in the industrial sectors for adequate manpower development. Therefore this research work is designed to assess the innovative materials resources for manpower development of brick/block laying and concreting trade students in technical colleges in Rivers State.

Statement of Problem

Manpower development has increasingly contributed in preparing knowledgeable students to meet the industrial age to information age in brick/block laying and concreting programmes globally. It is observed that technological trend involves digitalization of industries, whereby some industries utilize technology driven machines. With this development, develop countries have restructured the educational programmes to incorporate innovative strategies as resources so that graduates can be able to fit into the employment world. Unfortunately, Nigeria educational system has failed in this regard as some graduate find it difficult to cope in industries. This is why some companies engage their newly employed in training. Attesting to this, Dokubo (2017) lamented that technical education students are not fully equipped with innovative skills, hence they find it difficult to cope in industries in this technological era. Therefore, there is need for technical school to initiate innovative resources

that will enable students acquire innovative skill for employment after graduation. It is against the backdrop that the researcher deems it necessary to carry out the research on assessment of innovative material resources for manpower development of brick/block laying and concreting trade students in Technical Colleges in Rivers State.

Purpose of the Study

The study assessed the innovative materials resources for manpower development of brick/block laying and concreting trade students in technical colleges in Rivers State. Specifically, the study sought to;

1. determine the innovative tools for manpower development of brick/block laying and concreting trade students in technical colleges in Rivers State.
2. ascertain the innovative instructional materials for manpower development of brick/block laying and concreting trade students in technical colleges in Rivers State.
3. examine the innovative machines for manpower development of brick/block and concreting trade students in technical colleges in Rivers State.

Research Question

Based on the stated purpose the following research question guided the study.

1. What are the innovative tools for manpower development of brick/block laying and concreting trade students in technical colleges in Rivers State?
2. What are the innovative instructional materials for manpower development of brick/block laying and concreting trade students in technical colleges in Rivers State?
3. What are the innovative machines for manpower development of brick/block laying and concreting trade students in technical colleges in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at .05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant difference between the mean response of teachers and instructors on innovative tools for manpower development of brick/block laying and concreting trade students in technical colleges in Rivers State.
2. There is no significant difference between the mean response of teachers and instructors on innovative instructional materials for manpower development of brick/block laying and concreting trade students in technical colleges in Rivers State.
3. There is no significant difference between the mean response of teachers and instructors on innovative machines for manpower development of brick/block laying and concreting trade students in technical colleges in Rivers State.

METHODOLOGY

The study was carried out in technical colleges in Rivers State is known for crude oil exploration activities. Thus, there are different technical colleges such as Government technical college, Ahoda, Government Teacher College, Port Harcourt, Government Technical College, Ele-Ogu with several teachers and instructors of brick/block laying and concreting trade domiciled in the region. Therefore, this region was used for the study because adequate sample size can be assured. The study adopted descriptive survey design. The population of the study consisted of 15 brick/block laying and concreting teachers and 10 instructors respectively. The entire population was used and therefore no sampling was adopted. The instrument used for the study was a self made questionnaire tagged "Assessment of Innovative Materials Resources for Manpower Development of Brick/block laying and concreting trade in Technical College in Rivers State (AIMRMDBBLCTSTC). The instrument was structured in the pattern of 5 points likert scale of agreement and was validated by two experts in the Development of vocational and technology Education in Rivers State University, Port-Harcourt. The reliability of the instrument was established through test –re-test method and was computed using Parson Product Moment of Correlation. The reliability co-efficient achieved was. 82. Mean and standard deviation tool were used to answer the research questions, while t-test was used to test the hypotheses. Mean value less than 3.00 was rejected whole mean scores equal or greater than 3.00 were accepted. Meanwhile, t-calculated values less than t-critical were accepted while t-calculated greater than t- critical were rejected.

RESULTS AND FINDINGS

Research Question 1: *What are the innovative tools of brick/block laying and concreting trade students in technical colleges in Rivers State?*

Table 1: Mean Scores on Innovative Tool of Brick/Block Laying and Concreting Trade Students in Technical Colleges

S/N	Variables	Teachers (n=15)			Instructors (n=10)		
		\bar{X}_1	SD ₁	Decision	\bar{X}_2	SD ₂	Decision
1.	Measuring wheel	3.14	0.26	Agree	3.77	0.61	Agree
2.	Polishers	3.84	0.12	Agree	3.51	0.19	Agree
3.	Vacuum blower	3.79	0.15	Agree	3.31	1.22	Agree
4.	Bump cutter	3.41	1.34	Agree	3.88	0.33	Agree
5.	Screed scratchers	3.88	0.11	Agree	3.55	0.43	Agree
6.	Vibrator	3.37	0.29	Agree	3.48	0.55	Agree
7.	Plumb bob	3.48	0.96	Agree	3.64	0.61	Agree
8.	Barth rammer	3.50	0.46	Agree	3.60	0.54	Agree
9.	End frame	3.49	0.35	Agree	3.59	0.38	Agree
10.	Paddle mixer	3.60	0.19	Agree	3.91	0.28	Agree
Grand M & SD		3.55	0.42		3.63	0.51	

Source: Field survey, 2025, X=Mean; SD=Standard deviation, ≥ 3.00 accept, otherwise reject

Result in Table 1 on the innovative tools for manpower development of brick/block laying and concreting trade student showed teachers and instructors agreed that all items highlighted are innovative tools. This is based on the grand mean scores of 3.44 and 3.63 respectively, which are above 3.00 that was earlier stated to be the acceptable mean, also the grand means score for each of the item showed a high level of acceptance for each of the item by each group. Furthermore, the closeness in the Standard Deviation for the two groups which is 42. And .51 indicated homogeneity in their response. This finding agrees with Sandandam (2022) that every brick/block laying and concreting innovative tools are necessary in the construction industry to achieve a good result.

Research Question 2: *What are the innovative instructional materials for manpower development of brick/block laying and concreting trade students in technical colleges in Rivers State?*

Table 2: Mean Scores on Innovative Instructional Materials for Manpower Development of Brick/Block laying and Concreting Trade Students in Technical Colleges

S/N	Variables	Teachers (n=15)			Instructors (n=10)		
		\bar{X}_1	SD ₁	Decision	\bar{X}_2	SD ₂	Decision
11.	Virtual and augmented reality (VA/AR)	3.37	0.17	Agree	3.48	0.16	Agree
12.	Project visualization	3.99	1.13	Agree	3.92	0.11	Agree
13.	Building formation modeling (BIM)	3.88	0.23	Agree	3.74	1.29	Agree
14.	Simulation software	3.68	0.54	Agree	3.83	0.48	Agree
15.	3D printing and robotic	3.77	0.81	Agree	3.90	0.72	Agree
16.	Drowns and lidar	3.84	0.61	Agree	3.69	0.42	Agree
17.	Digital twins	3.56	0.33	Agree	3.58	0.62	Agree
18.	Physical model and mock-ups	3.59	0.19	Agree	3.46	0.13	Agree
19.	Gamified learning models	3.80	0.31	Agree	3.60	0.39	Agree
20.	Web based XR plat-forms	3.71	0.44	Agree	3.81	0.55	Agree
Grand M & SD		3.69	0.49		3.71	0.30	

Source: Field survey, 2025, X=Mean; SD=Standard deviation, ≥ 3.00 accept, otherwise reject

Result in Table 2 on innovative instructional materials for manpower development of brick/block laying and concreting trades students in Rivers State, showed that, teachers and instructors agreed that all the items highlighted are innovative instructional materials for manpower development of brick/block laying an concerting trade students. This is based on the grand mean scores of 3.69 and 3.71 respectively, which is above 3.00 that was earlier stated to be the acceptable mean. Also the grand mean scores for each of the items by each group furthermore, the closeness in Standard

Deviation for the two groups which is .49 and .38 indicated homogeneity in their responses. This finding is in line with Nwori (2020) that example of instructional resources include variety of sources and media format including online resources such as text, print photos, graphics, animation, simulations, sounds, videos and among others.

Research Questions 3: *What are the innovative Machine for manpower development of brick/block laying and concreting trade students in technical colleges in Rivers State?*

Table 2: Mean Scores on Innovative Machine for Manpower Development of Brick/Block laying and Concreting Trade Students in Technical Colleges

S/N	Variables	Teachers (n=15)			Instructors (n=10)		
		\bar{X}_1	SD ₁	Decision	\bar{X}_2	SD ₂	Decision
21.	Hydraulic power brick making machine	3.37	0.68	Agree	3.72	0.69	Agree
22.	Hydraulic power block making machine	3.56	0.52	Agree	3.51	0.50	Agree
23.	Concrete floor gathering machine	3.30	0.31	Agree	3.49	0.18	Agree
24.	High efficiency electric wall screed plaster machine	3.68	0.26	Agree	3.81	0.77	Agree
25.	Self landing concrete mixer	3.99	0.40	Agree	3.85	0.13	Agree
26.	Mobile concrete plant mixer	3.21	0.18	Agree	3.88	0.21	Agree
27.	Automatic rendering machine	3.16	0.12	Agree	3.61	0.17	Agree
28.	Plaster spraying machine	3.47	0.15	Agree	3.66	0.94	Agree
29.	Interlocking making machine	3.17	0.19	Agree	3.75	0.16	Agree
30.	Automatic plastering machine	3.13	0.20	Agree	3.55	1.10	Agree
Grand M & SD		3.40	0.30		3.68	0.85	

Source: Field survey, 2025, X=Mean; SD=Standard deviation, ≥ 3.00 accept, otherwise reject

Result in Table 3 on innovative machines for manpower development of brick/block laying and concreting trade student in Rivers State, showed that teachers and instructors agreed that all the items highlighted are innovative Machine for manpower development of brick/block laying and concreting trade students. This is based on the grand mean scores of 3.40 and 3.68 respectively, which is above 3.00 that was early stated to be the acceptable mean. Also the grand mean scores for each of the items shows a high level of acceptance for each of the item by each group. Furthermore, the closeness in the standard deviation for the two group is .30 and .85 shows homogeneity in the response. This finding agrees with United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (NESCO) (2019) that most developments in brick/block laying and concreting trades are the innovative machines that can make job easier in construction process.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between the mean responses of teachers and instructors on innovative tools for manpower development of brick/block laying and concreting trade students in technical colleges in Rivers State.

Table 4: t-Test Analysis on Innovative Tools for Manpower Development of Brick/Block Laying and Concreting Trade Students in Technical Colleges

Categories	n	\bar{x}	SD	α	df	Z-cal	Z-crit	Decision
Teachers	15	3.55	0.42	0.05	23	0.41	2.07	Not significant
Instructors	10	3.63	0.51					

Source: Field survey, 2025. Accept Ho if t-cal < t-crit otherwise reject

Table 4 showed that teachers had the mean and standard derivation scores of 3.55 and .42 respectively, while the instructors had the mean and standard deviation scores of 3.63 and .51 respectively. The t-cal value obtained was .42 while the t-crit was 2.07 with DF=23 at .05 level of significance for two tailed test. This result showed that t-cal. Was less than t-crit, which means that the null hypothesis was accepted. Thus there was no significant difference between the mean responses of teachers and instructors on the innovative tools for manpower development of brick/block laying and concreting trade students in technical colleges in Rivers State.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significance difference between the mean response of teachers and instructors on innovative materials for manpower development of brick/block laying and concreting trade students in technical colleges in Rivers State.

Table 5: t-Test Analysis on Innovative Materials for Manpower Development of Brick/Block Laying and Concreting Trade Students in Technical Colleges

Categories	n	\bar{x}	SD	α	df	Z-cal	Z-crit	Decision
Teachers	15	3.55	0.42	0.05	23	0.11	2.07	Not significant
Instructors	10	3.63	0.51					

Source: *Field survey, 2025.* Accept Ho if t-cal < t-crit otherwise reject.

Table 5 showed that teachers had the mean and standard deviation scores of 3.69 and .49 respectively. While instructors had the mean and standard deviation scores of 3.71 and .38 respectively. The t-cal value obtained was .11 while the t-crit was 2.07 with DF=23 at .05 level of the significance for two tailed test. This result showed that t-cal was less than t-crit, which means that the null hypothesis was accepted. Thus there was no significance difference between the mean and responses of teachers and instructors on the innovative machines for manpower development of brick/block laying and concreting trade students in technical colleges in Rivers State.

Hypothesis 3

There is no significance difference between the mean response of teachers and instructors on innovative machines for manpower development of brick/block laying and concreting trade students in technical colleges in Rivers State.

Table 6: t-Test Analysis on Innovative Materials for Manpower Development of Brick/Block Laying and Concreting Trade Students in Technical Colleges

Categories	n	\bar{x}	SD	α	df	Z-cal	Z-crit	Decision
Teachers	15	3.55	0.42	0.05	23	1.00	2.07	Not significant
Instructors	10	3.63	0.51					

Source: *Field survey, 2025.* Accept Ho if t-cal < t-crit otherwise reject.

Table 6 showed that teachers had the mean and standard deviation scores of 3.40 and .30 respectively. While instructors had the mean and standard deviation scores of 3.68 and .85 respectively. The t-cal value obtained was 1.00 while the t-crit was 2.07 with DF=23 at .05 level of the significance for two tailed test. This result showed that t-cal was less than t-crit, which means that the null hypothesis was accepted. Thus there was no significance difference between the mean and responses of teachers and instructors on the innovative machines for manpower development of brick/block laying and concreting trade students in technical colleges in Rivers State.

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that, measuring wheel, polishers, vacuum blower, bump cutter/screed and others were the innovative tools for manpower development of brick/block laying concreting trade students. More so, simulation software, virtual and augmented reality (VA/AR), digital twins and others were the innovative instructional materials for manpower development of brick/block laying and concreting trade students. However, Hydraulic paver brick/block molding machines, concrete floor grinding machine, high electric wall screeding plaster machine and others were innovative machines for manpower development of brick/block laying and concrete trade students.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made.

1. Government should ensure that the expected innovative tools, machines and instructional materials are provided in brick/block laying and concreting trade programmes for adequate manpower development.
2. Educators of brick/block laying and concreting trade should ensure that innovative instructional materials are used during students' practical activities to enhance manpower development.

3. Government should ensure that innovative machines are incorporated in brick/block laying and concrete trade programmes for manpower development, so that students will not face difficulties when they come across them in constructions industry.

REFERENCES

- Anyonike, C.S., Okelle, P.C. & Okeke, B.C. (2015). Development and evaluation of brick/block laying and concreting (B/BC) constructional video. *Journal of the Faculty of Engineering and Architecture of Gazi University*, 2(2), 217-227.
- Awurum, C.S. (2005). *Analysis of resources for the teaching and learning of block laying and concrete work at the Technical Colleges Level. a case study of Edo and Delta State* M.Ed Thesis in Technical Education Submitted to Post Graduate school, University of Benin.
- Dokubo, I.N. (2017). Technical and vocational education and training in South-South Nigeria: A veritable tool for the sustainable economic growth. *International Journal of Research Growtaalayah* 5(5), 34-41.
- National Board for Technical Education (2012). National Technical Certificate (N.T.C) and advanced National Technical Certificate (ANTC) Curriculum Courses Specification (Brick/Block Laying and Concreting) UNESCO- Nigeria.
- Nwafor, C.E. & Ali, F.O. (2015). TVET and local technologies for sustainable entrepreneurial in Innovation and Industrials Skills Development Nigeria South Eastern State. *International Journal of Humanities Social Science and Education* 2(7), 147-153.
- Nworie, G., Ilabor, A.I. & Salihu, A. (2020). Refocusing the Administration of Adult Education Programmes for Youth Empowerment in the 21st Century in Delta State, Nigeria (Paper presentation) 1st Annual Virtual Conference of Department of Vocational and Technology Education, Faculty of Education, Rivers State University Port Harcourt, Rivers State Nigeria.
- Obi-Anike, H.O., Otubruku, S.A. & Okafor C.N. (2017). Manpower Development and employee's performance: Qualitative assessment of small and medium scale business in Abuja Nigeria. *Journal of Economics, Management and Trade*, 18(3), 1-6.
- Sandanadam, .A. (2020). Types of Concrete Blocks or Concrete masonry unities user in construction. <https://theconductor.org<building>.
- United Nations, Educational, Scientific and cultural organization (UNESCO) (2019). Improving access, equity and relevance in technical vocational education and (TVET) synthesis report. Bangkok, Thailand.